

FEAST

Report on dietary behaviours

Report

D2.1

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Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

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Key Facts

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 List of acronyms and abbreviations

ELFI	EAT-Lancet Consumption Frequency Index
NCD	Non-Communicable Diseases
SSA	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
USG	University of Gastronomic Sciences
HEI	Heidelberg University
UCC	University College Cork
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
IPVC	Instituto Politecnico de Viana do Castelo

INTRODUCTION

Across Europe, current food systems often create a “Lose-Lose-Lose-Win” scenario—where large food corporations ‘Win’, while the environment, public health, government sectors, and small to medium-sized enterprises (such as farmers and local shops) ‘Lose’ (Jani et al, 2022). These systems contribute significantly to environmental degradation, accounting for 26% of global greenhouse gas emissions, using 50% of habitable land, consuming 70% of freshwater resources, causing 78% of eutrophication, and driving 60% of biodiversity loss (Xu et al, 2021). But the impact extends well beyond the environment. Today’s food systems play a central role in the rise of preventable diseases in both Europe and globally, placing indirect, yet substantial strain on public health systems and the economy. Furthermore, they exacerbate health inequalities across the EU, deepening disparities in access to nutritious and sustainable food (Xu et al, 2021).

Due to their complexity and dynamic nature, food systems pose significant challenges to the development and implementation of fair and sustainable policies. Much like ecosystems, they are shaped by an interplay of internal mechanisms and external pressures (Jani et al, 2022). A wide range of actors—operating across multiple geographic and temporal scales—bring diverse perspectives, interests, and values, which can lead to conflicts, tension, and uncertainty about the direction these systems may take in the future (Jessop et al, 2020). Important aspects such as behavioural patterns, communication dynamics around food, and their implications for fostering healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours are often overlooked (González-Gil et al, 2019).

Within the FEAST project, Work Package 2 (WP2), titled "*Mapping and Monitoring Dietary Patterns*", aimed to comprehensively map dietary patterns and food related behaviours in the European population. Its purpose was to fully capture which food groups are over- and under-consumed by adult population and the factors influencing their behaviours. By doing so, the analysed data would serve to inform policy and practice that could help shape a food system in which every person in Europe can easily eat a delicious, healthier and more sustainable diet. A higher adherence to a healthy and sustainable diet could reduce the risk of preventable non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and contribute to reducing the impact of the food system on environmental pollution and resource demand. All key food system stakeholders (individuals, the environment, the public sector and the private sector) could benefit, creating a ‘Win-Win-Win-Win’.

To support the transition to healthier and more sustainable food systems, the WP2 team designed a study on food purchasing and consumption habits, which delved into various aspects including adherence to the EAT-Lancet planetary health diet, food related behaviours, identification of perceived barriers and facilitators influencing healthy and sustainable dietary choices, and assessment of attitudes towards specific food system policies. This study was conducted through an online survey which garnered 27000 responses from 27 countries in the EU and geographical Europe. These countries included Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom.

This report reports the results of the WP2 study on the micro-level factors that influence individual food choices and behaviours, offering a detailed analysis of the geographic, socio-economic, behavioural, and cultural drivers that shape dietary habits at both the individual and group levels. It also examines the diversity of food environments across Food Regions in Europe and, where relevant data reveals limited access, it focuses on the unique dynamics affecting vulnerable populations. Additionally, the report includes results by “natural segments” found in Europe with different consumption patterns of healthy and sustainable food.

1. Methodology

Measures - The questionnaire on the food habits of Europeans was designed using sources in the grey and scientific literature (Murante et al, 2023). Firstly, the frequency scale for food consumption focuses on assessing adherence to the EAT-Lancet planetary health diet (Willet et al., 2019). It is used instead of a food intake frequency questionnaire, which are widely used in dietary research, because it increases compliance with large-scale cross-sectional surveys – namely, it takes less time for a respondent and, thus, increases the chances of getting completed surveys (Miranda et al, 2025).

Second, items dealing with food purchasing and consumption behaviour as well as the facilitators and barriers to the planetary health diet are derived from the results of the literature review exploration on healthy and sustainable food behaviours (Kapteijns et al, 2025) that was conducted during the early stages of WP2 work (Task 2.1) to complement a previous review on this topic (Kenny et al, 2023). Additionally, items have been introduced to explore people's attitude towards policies that either support or to ban actions at governmental and food system level. Additional details on the questionnaire design are described in Murante et al (2023).

Respondents - To explore factors that influence individual food choices among Europeans, to offer a detailed analysis at the geographic, and to represent the local population for its socio-economic characteristics, the WP2 team agreed to adopt a sample design strategy based on 1000 responses for each country distributed in quotas that consider sex, age, and educational attainment level of the above 27 European countries. The quotas calculation was based on EUROSTAT statistics for 2022. Respondents were enrolled in panels available in each country through CINT during the period from October 2024 to June 2025 and were asked to complete a web questionnaire. More details are available in Murante et al (2023).

Analysis – The results described in this report are the product of descriptive and cluster analyses mainly conducted on 25,802 questionnaires (out of the 27,417 questionnaires collected) including the demographics used to stratify the whole sample. This made it possible to weight the responses and return results as representative of the adult population of the 27 EU countries. To this end, sampling weights have been calculated. The remaining 1,615 questionnaires come from people who declared «not to identify» in one of the above two genders (Female or Male) or who preferred not to respond to the gender question, and they will be subsequently used to describe the food purchasing and consumption behaviours of this subgroup.

Descriptive analyses were used to examine the key sociodemographic characteristics of the population, consumption of different food groups, food purchasing behaviour, the perceived facilitators and barriers to healthy and sustainable diets, the support or opposition to specific food system policies, and the sources of information used by individuals to inform themselves about food. Results on food consumption were reported based on adherence to EAT-Lancet planetary health diet. It was possible by creating the ELFI index which translates the frequency of consumption in a measure of adherence to a healthy and sustainable diet (Miranda et al, 2025). The index was completed with two additional scores that measure the extent to which people consume food groups that are encouraged and food groups that should be balanced in the EAT Lancet planetary health diet.

Additional analyses were carried out to explore food choices and behaviors of Europeans as well as their intention to support different policies. Briefly, the research team of WP2 performed:

- Descriptive analysis (percentile distribution) and ANOVA (Box 1 and Box 4),
- Descriptive analyses (crosstab), analysis of means, comparative analysis (ANOVA, chi square tests) (Box 2),

- Descriptive analyses (crosstab, mean), linear regression and logistic regression models, Wilcoxon rank-sum tests to explore possible determinants of the use of information sources (Box 3).
- Descriptive analyses (crosstab, mean) and Multiple Correspondence Analysis (a descriptive, data reduction technique that displays associations among variable values in geometric space); Crosstabs (Box 5).
- Descriptive statistics and ordinal regression models (Box 6).

A cluster analysis was used to observe the population through homogenous segments for the food groups to encourage and the food groups to balance. Each segment is described with their sociodemographic characteristics, food purchasing behaviours and their perceived facilitators and barriers to eating a healthy and sustainable diet. Geographical maps show their distribution across the 27 countries. Furthermore, an aggregation of countries into regions is based on the food system typology that underlies FEAST that covers aspects including regional diets, welfare system characteristics (i.e. Beveridge or Bismarckian) and food production systems. The FEAST food regions include: Scandinavian, Anglo-Saxon, Central European, Eastern European and Southern European (Jani et al, 2022).

2. Respondents

The respondents were representative of Europeans living in the 27 EU countries considered for our study. Overall, 51.66% were female and the following distribution was seen for different age bands: 18-34 – 22.25%; 35-44 - 16.73%; 45-54 - 17.89%; 55-74 - 30.90%; and 75+ - 12.23%. Most of them (44.43%) had upper secondary or post-secondary education (ED3-4), less than a quarter (22.58%) had lower education (ED0-2), and a third had higher education (ED5-8). Respondents were composed of: two adults (32%) or two adults with at least one minor (20.42%); 20.9% single or 3.2% single with at least one minor; three or more adults (16.6%) or three or more adults with at least one minor (6.9%). In the household, a third of members were 65 year aged or more. The average number of household members was 2.6 and the average number of minors was 0.5.

Most respondents were employed (57.98%), a quarter were retired (24.82%) and a smaller proportion were unemployed (17.20%). The income data showed a higher participation of people in the first (41.35%) and fourth (22.65%) quartiles of the national income distribution. In the first quartile, an equal number (30.48%) of respondents perceived their household income as sufficient (30.00%) and insufficient respectively, while in the fourth quartile, most people (69.85%) perceived their income as sufficient for living.

More than half of the respondents said they lived in a city (38.50%) or a small town (27.27%), and 13.97% lived in the suburbs or outskirts of a big city. And for most of them, the city/suburb/small town was the place where they worked. Conversely, about one-fifth of respondents lived in the country (in a farm/house or village), but only half of them worked in the country.

Regarding the health status of respondents, 52.49% reported not having any pre-existing health conditions. Among healthy respondents only, only 7.73% were 75+. The remaining respondents reported: cardiovascular diseases (33.78%), mental illness (21.53%), musculoskeletal disorders (20.15%), metabolic disorders (17.82%), respiratory disorders (15.23%), gastrointestinal conditions (12.13%), cancer (5.64%) or other conditions (11.74%). In addition, the BMI reported by respondents shows that 45.01% had a normal weight, while 4.69% were underweight, 32.50% were overweight and 17.79% were obese. Obesity was twice as common in respondents with pre-existing health conditions.

3. Food purchasing and consumption

For food habits, over half of the respondents were always (54.4%) or often (28.6%) in charge of household grocery purchases, as well as always (47.4%) or often (26.3%) in charge of preparing meals in the household. They shopped in one supermarket (45%) or in two or more supermarkets (58%). About a quarter of people had the habit to buy food in an independent store (26.0%) or at local markets (23.0%). Only 9.1% bought directly from farmers, 18.8% shopped online and 4.7% used food banks or community larders.

Furthermore, 89.9% of respondents prepared their meals at home, while the consumption of ready-made meals (19.0%), takeaway food (11.7%) and meal delivery (9.5%) as well as eating at restaurants (10.6%) or at canteens (5.4%) was much less.

3.1 Healthy and sustainable diet: Europeans' food consumption

The adherence of Europeans to a healthy and sustainable diet is sufficient (24.1 point out of 42) according to the 14 EAT Lancet food groups (Figure 1). To-balance foods provided a consistent contribution to the overall ELFI score. At the geographical level, better results were observed in the Southern Food Region (25.8) (Italy (26.6), Greece (25.7) and Spain (25.1)). Similar results were observed in Bulgaria (24.6), Slovenia (24.5) and Switzerland (24.4).

Figure 1 ELFI score and to-balance foods score distribution by countries

Our results show that Europeans are far from fully adhering to the EAT Lancet planetary health diet. Higher adherence was observed among respondents for tubers (44.9%), poultry (44.5%), eggs (42.1%) and plant oils (31.0%) (Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.). The following graphs depict the levels of adherence to the planetary health diet for each food category. The different levels were categorized according to Miranda et al. (2025), where green represents a high adherence; yellow a medium adherence; orange a low adherence; red no adherence.

Figure 2 Level of adherence to the planetary health diet for foods to encourage

Figure 3 Level of adherence to the planetary health diet for foods to limit

Figure 4 Level of adherence to the planetary health diet for foods to balance

Table 3 Overall adherence to each food category across all 27 countries – for foods to encourage

Illustrates in more detail the overall adherence to each food category across all 27 countries. In this case, it shows the share of the population for each of the different levels. The highest percentage in every food category was highlighted per country to identify the dominant tendency of its population. The same logic of colours of Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. apply here.

Adherence to EAT Lancet		Country																											Total
		AT	BE	BG	CH	CZ	DE	DK	EE	ES	FI	FR	GR	HR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LV	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	SE	SL	SK	UK	
Whole grains	No	12,8	12,7	5,1	8,2	12,6	11,1	5,9	3,4	16,9	2,9	24,1	7,7	5,3	14,1	4,8	14,3	6,9	3,1	5,4	7,8	5,2	12,5	8,7	9,1	4,5	6,2	5,1	11,7
	Low	39,3	28,8	31,5	34,4	45,0	33,4	31,7	27,4	30,9	24,3	30,3	41,0	35,2	37,4	27,7	33,8	48,4	28,9	22,5	27,3	33,2	31,0	35,6	34,5	38,2	38,1	30,6	32,5
	Medium	34,4	31,1	31,9	38,7	33,5	34,6	34,4	39,9	29,7	33,1	29,0	32,5	40,3	33,0	41,1	33,5	33,4	35,9	33,0	36,0	35,5	27,9	34,5	34,9	38,4	37,8	38,8	33,7
	High	13,5	27,4	31,5	18,8	9,0	20,9	28,0	29,3	22,5	39,7	16,7	18,8	19,3	15,6	26,4	18,4	11,4	32,1	39,2	29,0	26,1	28,6	21,2	21,5	18,9	18,0	25,6	22,1
Vegetables	No	1,0	1,8	1,7	1,0	0,9	1,1	2,7	0,8	1,5	1,3	2,7	0,4	0,4	0,8	0,7	2,4	0,2	0,6	0,6	1,4	0,5	1,7	1,5	1,7	0,2	0,4	1,2	1,5
	Low	51,8	30,5	36,6	37,5	47,8	45,6	42,6	46,0	49,4	35,1	47,8	50,2	55,1	52,6	33,6	41,4	41,2	46,6	23,0	39,2	32,7	41,3	52,6	33,4	36,6	42,3	35,3	42,2
	Medium	41,8	57,5	48,9	50,3	44,5	45,7	45,5	43,9	42,6	50,4	43,5	43,1	41,3	39,1	51,3	41,7	51,8	45,6	65,9	49,8	55,1	44,5	39,8	52,2	56,1	50,0	51,8	47,0
	High	5,4	10,1	12,8	11,2	6,9	7,7	9,1	9,3	6,5	13,2	6,0	6,3	3,2	7,5	14,4	14,6	6,8	7,3	10,4	9,6	11,8	12,6	6,0	12,8	7,2	7,4	11,6	9,4
Fruits	No	4,1	2,5	2,2	1,8	1,0	1,7	4,7	1,2	1,7	2,2	4,1	1,0	0,5	0,9	2,3	3,0	0,2	1,6	2,3	2,3	0,5	1,6	0,2	3,2	0,6	0,4	2,3	2,2
	Low	41,7	40,0	41,5	40,4	45,9	37,6	45,6	42,1	27,9	40,0	40,2	44,1	46,5	46,2	36,0	28,7	48,4	46,7	27,6	46,2	34,1	20,6	44,4	41,7	35,1	40,3	37,4	36,4
	Medium	48,8	46,7	44,8	47,7	47,9	50,5	40,6	48,0	50,1	45,8	45,6	46,7	45,3	43,2	44,8	44,2	46,1	44,3	54,5	41,2	51,8	51,6	47,8	44,4	53,0	50,3	44,6	47,5
	High	5,4	10,9	11,5	10,2	5,2	10,3	9,1	8,8	20,3	12,1	10,1	8,3	7,7	9,7	16,8	24,2	5,4	7,4	15,6	10,4	13,6	26,2	7,6	10,7	11,3	9,1	15,7	13,9
Fish and shellfish	No	16,4	8,8	10,8	14,7	20,3	21,1	13,4	10,0	3,9	13,6	11,6	3,8	9,5	29,1	15,7	11,5	5,9	14,7	17,3	9,5	10,6	5,0	10,2	11,9	11,8	13,8	17,0	13,5
	Low	34,5	29,6	32,3	30,8	44,3	32,2	30,1	31,2	18,0	29,9	26,9	37,5	37,2	48,7	17,7	20,2	39,3	31,2	28,7	22,4	35,3	21,2	41,9	22,3	38,9	40,4	23,0	28,3
	Medium	29,8	32,1	32,9	27,6	25,6	29,4	25,2	27,9	30,3	29,3	34,9	41,1	35,3	12,1	26,0	36,0	32,8	23,4	34,3	25,1	34,0	21,8	26,9	33,9	34,2	30,2	29,9	31,2
	High	19,3	29,5	24,1	26,9	9,8	17,3	31,3	31,0	47,8	27,2	26,6	17,7	18,1	10,2	40,6	32,4	22,0	30,7	19,8	43,0	20,2	52,0	21,1	31,9	15,1	15,6	30,1	27,1
Legumes	No	11,2	15,5	4,0	9,5	8,3	10,1	23,1	12,8	1,9	17,0	8,4	2,0	3,0	4,2	14,6	5,0	6,3	10,9	12,8	19,8	7,1	4,2	3,1	17,0	3,9	2,5	20,0	9,3
	Low	36,3	29,9	27,2	29,2	41,7	33,6	29,0	35,9	10,0	35,4	28,3	16,5	28,9	47,5	19,9	15,6	43,1	32,5	31,1	32,6	42,8	15,9	30,8	27,5	28,3	32,6	22,5	27,0
	Medium	44,0	41,1	57,0	46,5	44,9	45,5	34,4	35,8	72,9	34,7	51,9	73,4	60,5	42,7	43,7	66,2	45,8	41,3	46,3	37,5	42,5	53,4	48,0	42,2	56,6	58,3	44,0	51,5
	High	8,5	13,5	11,8	14,8	5,1	10,9	13,5	15,6	15,1	12,9	11,5	8,2	7,6	5,6	21,9	13,2	4,9	15,3	9,9	10,2	7,7	26,6	18,1	13,3	11,3	6,6	13,5	12,2
Nuts	No	12,5	20,7	6,9	9,1	11,2	15,1	14,9	10,7	4,8	17,1	17,1	6,3	4,8	9,6	12,7	9,3	5,0	12,2	11,5	13,0	8,0	6,8	5,1	12,8	8,6	5,2	16,9	11,9
	Low	29,8	28,5	22,4	23,9	38,1	28,7	30,2	33,1	21,2	34,2	33,0	28,9	30,0	48,3	24,7	26,0	42,4	36,0	25,3	33,2	38,2	28,7	35,7	32,4	33,2	37,5	32,3	30,3
	Medium	38,5	33,7	46,9	42,6	38,0	35,5	33,7	39,7	46,1	28,9	35,6	41,4	45,6	31,6	38,7	43,2	39,3	32,7	44,1	35,2	36,9	38,8	42,8	36,4	43,3	44,3	33,6	38,4
	High	19,3	17,2	23,8	24,4	12,6	20,7	21,2	16,5	27,9	19,9	14,3	23,4	19,6	10,6	24,0	21,5	13,3	19,2	19,2	18,7	16,9	25,7	16,4	18,5	14,9	13,0	17,2	19,4
All plant oils and plant margarines	No	2,1	4,9	2,2	2,1	2,1	2,8	6,5	2,8	2,1	3,7	3,4	0,6	0,3	2,5	7,3	4,5	1,2	2,1	5,7	6,0	1,7	1,9	2,0	7,0	2,8	1,2	10,9	4,1
	Low	52,0	48,8	36,5	42,1	63,5	48,7	49,6	42,8	25,0	38,7	48,3	29,8	37,7	58,1	49,4	32,3	49,0	39,7	45,3	57,3	60,4	39,7	51,9	49,0	45,3	61,2	53,9	45,7
	Medium	23,3	23,4	20,9	22,1	18,7	24,8	19,8	22,4	15,3	17,6	20,6	15,8	26,1	21,2	19,5	14,9	21,9	25,4	20,2	17,5	19,8	19,0	18,9	19,6	19,1	18,6	15,1	19,2
	High	22,6	23,0	40,3	33,8	15,8	23,7	24,1	32,0	57,6	40,0	27,7	53,8	36,0	18,3	23,9	48,4	28,0	32,8	28,8	19,2	18,1	39,4	27,3	24,5	32,7	19,0	20,1	31,0

Table 4 Overall adherence to each food category across all 27 countries – for foods to limit and foods to balance

	Adherence to EAT Lancet	Country																											
		AT	BE	BG	CH	CZ	DE	DK	EE	ES	FI	FR	GR	HR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LV	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	SE	SL	SK	UK	Total
Animal fats and other saturated fats	No	16,3	17,1	15,9	17,6	15,6	28,9	22,6	20,6	10,0	19,0	23,6	10,0	13,2	12,7	27,1	6,5	21,0	21,7	20,5	19,6	29,3	22,3	11,6	26,0	13,2	18,3	18,7	19,1
	Low	43,5	44,6	28,8	43,6	51,3	35,0	40,2	43,2	28,4	33,0	41,6	29,7	46,8	44,6	38,1	26,9	45,6	43,2	36,3	39,2	40,4	31,9	42,5	42,2	40,3	47,2	32,9	36,1
	Medium	30,2	28,6	40,1	32,1	30,4	28,9	28,4	30,2	43,2	36,3	25,1	47,1	35,2	37,3	25,8	50,6	29,7	27,9	29,4	31,5	27,2	32,9	41,9	26,1	39,4	33,0	32,8	34,1
	High	10,0	9,7	15,2	6,7	2,7	7,2	8,8	6,1	18,4	11,7	9,7	13,3	4,8	5,5	9,0	16,0	3,8	7,3	13,7	9,7	3,1	12,9	4,0	5,8	7,1	1,5	15,6	10,7
Added sugars	No	23,4	20,8	30,9	19,9	27,3	22,5	22,1	30,2	27,9	26,1	22,0	21,7	31,7	23,8	23,6	28,1	32,3	35,8	24,8	15,7	28,3	29,9	27,6	18,8	22,0	24,6	22,0	24,6
	Low	40,1	35,2	35,6	38,4	38,9	36,5	36,3	36,5	28,7	35,1	34,3	34,7	34,2	34,2	35,3	28,3	32,1	33,1	36,9	40,2	36,3	32,0	37,0	39,0	33,8	43,8	32,4	34,1
	Medium	30,1	34,7	27,1	33,7	28,3	30,5	34,5	27,9	33,8	31,4	31,7	37,2	29,6	34,7	31,5	31,7	30,0	24,9	27,3	36,2	29,5	30,0	31,8	34,7	35,5	27,7	32,1	31,6
	High	6,4	9,3	6,5	8,0	5,5	10,5	7,1	5,5	9,6	7,5	12,1	6,3	4,5	7,3	9,6	12,0	5,6	6,2	11,0	7,9	5,9	8,1	3,7	7,6	8,7	3,9	13,5	9,8
Tubers or Starches	No	3,0	19,9	10,8	11,2	3,3	8,2	12,1	14,7	8,6	13,5	6,6	5,4	8,1	2,8	20,2	5,2	9,8	16,1	9,3	11,4	14,2	14,8	6,9	8,1	4,9	5,3	10,1	8,7
	Low	7,8	19,8	13,5	10,2	9,4	12,9	15,4	20,9	15,2	18,6	11,0	9,6	13,2	11,0	17,9	7,7	17,0	16,5	22,0	18,2	21,3	11,7	11,0	16,8	10,7	9,4	14,6	13,4
	Medium	33,1	28,6	25,8	31,7	40,4	35,3	27,8	32,1	38,3	33,6	32,0	29,8	42,6	28,0	32,1	28,4	32,4	34,1	32,6	32,7	33,7	29,2	28,9	33,2	41,4	37,2	34,2	33,0
	High	56,1	31,6	49,9	47,0	46,9	43,6	44,8	32,4	37,9	34,3	50,4	55,3	36,2	58,2	29,7	58,8	40,9	33,3	36,1	37,6	30,9	44,4	53,2	42,0	43,0	48,2	41,1	
Dairy Food	No	9,9	9,0	8,9	12,6	6,4	10,3	13,5	11,1	25,0	24,1	12,7	6,8	6,3	10,3	21,4	9,2	4,2	10,1	15,5	16,9	8,1	13,8	5,3	18,4	7,7	6,9	23,9	13,6
	Low	53,8	51,3	50,1	50,7	49,9	56,3	50,5	49,3	52,2	51,2	53,9	54,1	51,7	49,4	45,6	40,8	40,7	43,8	59,0	50,5	49,5	54,1	48,1	57,0	52,0	52,5	48,3	51,0
	Medium	20,5	22,2	23,5	19,2	28,7	18,1	14,8	23,4	11,8	13,1	17,9	20,4	24,5	22,8	16,9	25,4	27,9	23,9	13,3	16,4	25,3	14,9	26,9	14,4	23,5	25,1	14,5	19,1
	High	15,8	17,5	17,5	17,5	15,0	15,4	21,2	16,2	10,9	11,7	15,5	18,8	17,5	17,5	16,1	24,6	27,2	22,3	12,2	16,2	17,1	17,2	19,7	10,3	16,8	15,5	13,3	16,3
Beef, lamb, goat, pork, and red meat in its processed form	No	8,3	16,2	15,3	9,1	6,9	8,8	18,4	22,8	12,5	22,2	11,4	6,2	8,6	8,9	17,4	5,4	18,7	22,8	16,4	9,0	11,0	19,4	14,5	11,5	7,8	8,7	9,5	10,6
	Low	13,6	25,1	15,5	17,5	17,1	14,4	24,4	23,0	17,2	19,3	18,3	11,8	18,8	14,3	18,8	9,1	21,0	18,8	22,6	17,3	20,6	20,1	16,9	22,8	17,2	14,7	19,9	16,9
	Medium	53,1	46,4	49,6	53,2	57,3	54,7	43,7	44,1	58,8	40,4	52,9	63,7	59,1	49,5	51,9	66,4	43,3	45,9	45,9	54,5	50,8	42,0	51,6	46,6	55,3	57,4	50,5	54,1
	High	25,1	12,4	19,6	20,2	18,8	22,1	13,5	10,1	11,6	18,1	17,5	18,3	13,5	27,4	11,9	19,2	16,9	12,5	15,1	19,2	17,6	18,6	17,0	19,1	19,7	19,2	20,1	18,4
Chicken and other poultry	No	4,1	11,2	11,0	7,5	4,0	6,0	8,1	14,0	10,0	8,5	6,9	3,2	7,1	7,5	16,8	4,9	9,1	10,4	9,6	6,5	6,8	16,9	11,8	6,0	5,9	5,8	10,7	7,8
	Low	6,5	16,4	12,5	13,1	7,7	9,1	15,2	19,2	15,2	14,9	11,6	9,2	18,7	14,6	19,3	9,5	15,3	24,2	14,1	11,9	15,7	22,5	12,2	11,9	10,6	11,5	16,6	12,8
	Medium	24,0	31,1	34,5	29,3	33,5	26,3	31,8	32,4	41,8	36,8	35,8	29,9	39,4	40,9	37,7	38,5	39,6	31,2	33,0	31,7	38,6	38,4	36,3	30,5	39,3	37,3	37,9	35,0
	High	65,3	41,3	42,0	50,1	54,8	58,7	44,9	34,4	33,0	39,8	45,7	57,6	34,8	37,0	26,2	47,0	36,1	34,1	43,2	49,9	39,0	22,3	39,7	51,7	44,2	45,5	34,8	
Eggs	No	9,2	7,7	15,1	10,9	5,8	9,2	13,1	15,9	10,5	11,6	6,0	10,8	5,5	8,8	20,8	3,5	10,9	15,9	10,2	14,6	10,7	16,8	15,5	15,5	9,6	7,7	9,6	9,2
	Low	10,5	10,3	15,1	14,0	10,5	12,7	14,8	18,2	17,5	10,1	11,4	10,7	11,7	14,9	17,2	5,2	17,3	13,6	12,9	16,4	16,6	18,9	16,3	14,3	10,9	11,8	12,9	12,7
	Medium	32,6	28,4	32,9	30,5	43,1	32,7	30,5	31,9	48,9	31,1	32,2	37,8	40,6	40,5	32,7	33,3	38,0	40,4	34,0	30,4	42,3	37,2	43,4	31,9	42,0	38,1	34,0	36,0
	High	47,7	53,5	37,0	44,7	40,6	45,3	41,6	34,0	23,1	47,2	50,4	40,6	42,2	35,8	29,3	58,0	33,8	30,1	43,1	38,7	30,5	27,1	24,8	38,3	37,5	42,4	43,6	

Czechia's low adherence was observed for consumption of wholegrains, vegetables, fish and legumes (less than 10%). Of concern is the low percentage of full adherence to recommendations for sugars (9.8%); higher levels of adherence to recommended sugar consumption was seen in the UK (13.5%), France (12.1%), Italy (12.0%) and Germany (10.5%), though this is still very low. There was also very low adherence to recommended vegetable consumption (9.4%); higher vegetable adherence was seen in Italy (14.6%) and Ireland (14.4%). In particular, the Southern food region generally had low adherence to the recommendations for whole grains and vegetables. The Scandinavian and Anglo-Saxon food regions generally had low adherence to recommendations for fruit, legumes and dairy. The Central Food Region generally had low adherence to recommendations for legumes and animal fats and other saturated fats. The Eastern Food Region generally had low adherence to recommendations for legumes, animal fats and other saturated fats, all vegetable oils, and often to added sugars. Adherence to recommendations for fish consumption was particularly critical for Czech Republic and Hungary. Likewise, adherence to recommendations for tuber consumption were critical for Poland, Latvia and Estonia. And there was low adherence to red meat recommendations in Ireland, Finland, Belgium, Portugal, Latvia and Estonia.

Our findings of dietary behaviour are not aligned with our finding that 61.2% of the respondents reported that they ate a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Box 1 – Summary Insights on Europeans' diet

What we learned from our in depth analyses of Europeans' diets

Topic	Insights
<p>Most Europeans do not adhere to the planetary health diet</p>	<p><i>Among people with the least virtuous diet, a great deal of diversification in the frequency of consumption of different food groups was observed across the FEAST Food Regions. For example, Scandinavians consumed significantly lower amounts of legumes and unsaturated fats (e.g. from vegetable oils and nuts). They also consumed legumes and fish infrequently.</i></p> <p><i>Despite being the group with the highest sugar consumption, people in the Southern European food region were the most virtuous in terms of fat consumption because they had the lowest saturated fat consumption and the highest unsaturated fat consumption (probably due to their high consumption of vegetable oils). Moreover, they also showed the highest consumption of fruit, legumes, fish and nuts but it was still much less than what is recommended in the planetary health diet.</i></p> <p><i>Generally, the analysis on the sociodemographic characteristics of individuals with low, medium and high adherence to the planetary health diet reveals that the three groups were largely homogenous in their distributions of sex, age bands and education level; hence, the adherence to a sustainable and healthy diet seems to be independent of demographics.</i></p>

3.2 What Europeans consider when purchasing or consuming food

Marketing science has found that purchasing and consumption processes vary for different individuals. Kapteijns et al., (2025). Recent evidence also demonstrates other factors linked to the environment are also increasingly influencing consumer choices (Brunin et al., 2022).

Europeans consider food pleasure, convenience and eating and purchasing habits as drivers of their choices (Figure 5). Consumers frequently considered value for money (39.9% "always" and 42.5% "often") when making a purchase, especially if they were over 34 years old. People bought or consumed foods that were available where they usually shop (28.6% "always" and 45.8% "often"), that they were used to eating (29.2% "always" and 50.6% "often"), and that were easy to prepare (16.1% "always" and 40.8% "often"). They also always (33.7%) or often (41.9%) considered overall product appeal (appearance, smell, taste, flavor, texture). Furthermore, they looked at the size of the package when buying food (17.4% "always" and 39.4% "often"). Finally, the religious dimension was less relevant (60.4% "never" or 11.6% "rarely") used this as a factor in determining their decisions, especially if they were under 45 years old.

Health, sustainability and ethical issues also influenced respondents' food choices (Figure 5). When buying or consuming food, people often considered the following elements: a clear list of ingredients (21.5% "always" and 37.0% "often"), and their nutritional value (15.2% "always" and 33.1% "often"). The latter was more frequently considered by young adults (35-44 year old) and elderly (75 years old and more). Equally important to them was knowing the country of origin of the food (19.6% "always" and 30.7% "often"), respect for the seasonality of the food (18.5% "always" and 38.3% "often"), the use of environmentally friendly packaging (10.8% "always" and 26.3% "often") and their impact on the environment (10.3% "always" and 22.3% "often"). No less important were ethical issues, such as the conditions of workers in the food production system. Factors that have direct impact on the environment (e.g. greenhouse gas emission) were more frequently considered by younger people, while adults and elderly considered elements like country of origin, local production and seasonality of food more frequently. Overall, the above factors were considered more by women than men.

Box 2 provides a further general summary of the findings of drivers of food purchasing and consumption based on different demographic factors including sex, education level and income.

Figure 5 Factors considered during the food purchasing or consumption process ('Often' and 'Always' responses)

 Box 2 – Further insights on *factors considered during food purchasing or consumption*.

What we learned from our in depth analyses factors considered during purchasing/consumption

Topic	Insights
Factors considered during food purchasing or consumption by different socio-demographics	<p>Notable differences emerged when considering sex, education level and income:</p> <p>Women tended to be more sensitive to environmental concerns and seasonality, and were more likely to conform to social norms when making food choices. Men, on the other hand, were less likely to consider these factors as much as women but they did show a higher level of consideration for religious beliefs relative to women in their food purchasing and consumption decisions.</p> <p>Higher education levels correlated with an increased emphasis on local production, nutritional value, product origin and seasonality.</p> <p>Individuals who perceived their income as insufficient displayed the least interest in environmental concerns, such as eco-friendly packaging, sustainability certifications and seasonality, and religious beliefs. Instead, their food choices were primarily guided by the balance between price and quality, familiarity, and overall product appeal, highlighting a more pragmatic, necessity-driven approach.</p> <p>When examining food purchasing and consumption patterns, the data highlights a convenience- and habit-driven approach by consumers. The most influential factors included good price-quality ratio, familiarity with foods (habit-driven choices), overall product appeal, and availability in usual shopping locations.</p> <p>At a secondary level, transparency and awareness emerged as relevant concerns, with consumers paying attention to ingredient clarity, nutritional value, seasonality, and local production. Additionally, social influence played a role with eating habits of others contributing to individual choices, suggesting a certain degree of conformism.</p> <p>Environmental and ethical concerns were cited but were less prominent, ranking below price, familiarity, and availability. The least relevant factor in food choices was religious belief.</p>
Factors considered during food purchasing or consumption across European Food Regions	<p>Breaking down food choice behaviors by region reveals notable differences:</p> <p>Consumers in the Scandinavian food region showed the least concern for environmental and ethical factors, prioritizing convenience and availability instead.</p> <p>Anglo-Saxon food region consumers also prioritized pragmatism and convenience, though they placed greater importance on maintaining established eating habits.</p> <p>Eastern European food region consumers shared this habit-driven approach, but displayed less concern for food transparency.</p> <p>Southern European food region consumers valued ingredient transparency, seasonality and local production, and displayed a food culture influenced by social factors.</p>

Central European food region consumers struck a balance, with seasonality and habit-based convenience playing key roles.

These regional differences aligned with the observed perceptions of sustainability. Scandinavian food region consumers not only scored the lowest in terms of perceived diet sustainability, but also showed the least interest in ethical and environmental food concerns. Meanwhile, Southern European food region consumers exhibited higher awareness and placed greater emphasis on food transparency and origin.

3.3 Source of nutritional information

The most common source for nutrition information for Europeans was family (51%) and many also consulted online resources (40%) more frequently than traditional media (32.2%). Consumer-related sources like supermarkets, food labels or food packaging were used by 33.4% of people. Friends, peers or neighbors were a source of information for 31.5% of respondents, and 27.6% of respondents said health professionals were a source of information. Government resources and schools were a source of information on food nutrition for 11.2% and 7.6% of respondents, respectively.

Box 3 – Further insights on sources of nutrition information

What we learned from our in depth analyses about sources of info

Topic	Insights
Source of information and consumers' profile	<p><i>For most sources, education level and income influenced the use of each food information source. People with lower education level more often reported using their family as an information source for decisions about food. People with higher education levels more often reported using traditional media, digital media, healthcare professionals, consumer related sources & health/government authorities. Education level did not significantly influence the use of friends/peers and school/work as a source. Additionally, the respondents with higher family income also reported using a higher the number of sources of information. Across Europe it was observed that the average number of food information sources used was the highest in the Anglo Saxon food region and lowest in Central Europe.</i></p> <p><i>Personal knowledge on healthy and sustainable diets supported individuals in eating healthier and more sustainable diets less when using their family or their friends as a source of information, and more when using traditional media, digital media, healthcare professionals, consumer related source and government/health authorities.</i></p>

4. Factors supporting Europeans to eat healthily and sustainably

Europeans reported that social support played a supportive role in driving them to consume healthier and more sustainable diets (Figure 6). 47.1% of respondents reported a 5 or 4 score¹ that this was when they considered the eating habits of people they shared meals with and 43.7% of respondents reported that the expectations of people who are important to them guided their consumption decisions. Conversely, only 27.5% agreed on benefiting from external pressure from social media, policy, social campaigns, or healthy eating guidelines by reporting a 5 or 4 score. Finally, 35% of respondents said that practical support tools were helpful, as was the availability of information on sustainable and ethical food production (43.3%).

Individuals had personal resources that could contribute to the adherence to healthy and sustainable diets. A respondent’s personal goal to improve health (65.8%) and their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets (56.3%) completely or almost completely supported them in eating healthily and more sustainably, as did the availability of healthy and sustainable food choices where they usually shop or eat (56.1%).

Figure 6 Factors supporting healthy and sustainable diets (Scores 4 and 5²)

Box 4 – Further insights on facilitators of healthy and sustainable diets.

What we learned from our in depth analyses on facilitators

Topic	Insights
Food frequency consumption and facilitators	<i>For those who reported higher adherence to the planetary health diet, there was a stronger effect of exposure to or living in an environment that facilitates the adoption of healthier and more sustainable diets. The most relevant facilitators were knowledge of healthy and sustainable diets, availability of practical support tools (e.g. menu guides, apps and scoring systems), personal health improvement goals and information on the sustainable and ethical production of food items.</i>

¹ A 5 point Likert scale was used, from 1 “Not at all” to 5 “Completely”

² People answered using a Likert scale from 1 to 5 (1=Not at all and 5= Completely)

5. Factors limiting Europeans to eat healthily and sustainably

The unaffordability of healthy and sustainable foods was seen as the most consistent barrier to healthy and sustainable eating (Figure 7 - reported by 45.3% of respondents completely or almost completely). Similarly, the unavailability of healthy and sustainable food options close to where people lived or worked limited the ability of 21.8% of Europeans to eat a healthy and sustainable diet. Daily life activities and relationship also played a role in eating habits. In this regard, individuals report that their difficulties in preparing healthy and sustainable food (27.0%) limited their ability to eat healthily and sustainably. A third of respondents were limited by their irregular work hours (34.3%) or busy lifestyles (37.3%) and by the eating habits of people they shared meals with (22.2%). Other factors that negatively impacted respondents were food preferences, neophobia, psychology and food knowledge: Europeans reported giving up foods they liked (34.5%), eating strange or unusual food (25.0%), a lack of willpower (31.4%) and their lack of knowledge about healthy and sustainable eating (21.1%) as additional obstacles.

Figure 7 Factors limiting adherence to healthy and sustainable diets (Scores 4 and 5³)

³ People answered using a Likert scale from 1 to 5 (1=Not at all and 5= Completely)

 Box 5 – Further insights on barriers to adherence to healthy and sustainable diets.

What we learned from our in depth analyses about barriers

Topic	Insights
Food frequency consumption and barriers	<p data-bbox="427 394 1353 645"><i>It was observed that barriers influenced dietary behaviours less than facilitators. The strongest effects were found for the following barriers: unaffordability; giving up foods one likes; lack of willpower; difficulty preparing healthy and sustainable meals; strange or unusual foods. As expected, individuals with higher scores for adherence to the planetary health diet reported experiencing fewer difficulties in adherence to healthy and sustainable diets.</i></p> <p data-bbox="427 656 1353 983"><i>Furthermore, our findings showed that most Europeans chose foods based on what they liked and were used to, and that a considerable proportion of Europeans considered giving up foods they liked as a barrier to eating a healthy and sustainable diet. We also observed that the influence of taste preferences, as well as the social and personal environment on the adoption of a healthy and sustainable diet were not perceived differently by men and women, or by people with different educational attainments. Instead, meaningful differences in these perceptions were found by age and the degree to which healthy and sustainable food was perceived as unaffordable.</i></p>

6. Food policies

Europeans were also asked to express their opinions on government policies (less than 10% of respondents preferred to not respond) aimed at promoting healthy and sustainable food systems and, thus, diets; results showed they are slightly more likely to support them. **Their Support is higher for policies targeting unhealthy foods typically consumed by young people (Figure 8)**, such as: banning the sale of energy drinks to people under the age of 18 (62.6%); banning the marketing of unhealthy foods and drinks to children through the use of cartoon characters and other appealing elements on packaging (51.2%) or in the media (social media, internet, TV, radio, newspapers and magazines) (42.4%).

Supporters of these policies were mainly found in: Bulgaria (62.2%), to ban marketing in all media; Bulgaria (68.4%) and Latvia (65.6%), to ban marketing using cartoon characters; Romania (82.7%), Croatia (81.9%) and Bulgaria (80.3%), to ban the sale of energy drinks. A higher percentage of support was for policies aimed at healthy and sustainable eating in young people (69.6%) and were distributed between respondents in countries as follows: France (16.5%), Germany (13.3%), the UK (12%), Italy (9.9%), Spain (9.0%) and Poland (8.9%).

Figure 8 Supporters of policies influences on diets of young people

Europeans exhibited awareness of the negative effects of some promotional strategies with their support on banning outdoor advertising (e.g. at bus stops) (44.5%) and the presence of unhealthy foods and drinks at supermarket checkouts (40.6%) (Figure 9). There was a higher consensus in Bulgaria (53.8%), Poland (51.4%), Romania (50.2%) and Ireland (49.8%) to ban unhealthy products at supermarket checkouts. And a higher consensus in Bulgaria (59%), France (55.6%), Romania (55.5%), Slovenia (53.0%) and Latvia (51.4%), to ban outdoor advertisements. Both policies were supported by 70.3% of respondents in Europe, distributed across countries as follows: France (14.0%), Germany (13.2%), UK (12.9%), Italy (12.4%), Spain (8.9%) and Poland (8.9%).

Figure 9 Supporters of policies addressing promotion strategies of unhealthy/unsustainable foods

There are governmental actions that have demonstrated to be effective in other fields (e.g. tobacco) to change individual behaviors. **Europeans seemed keen to support policies that use regulatory nudging and other approaches to reduce the impact of the food industry on health and the environment (Figure 10 and Figure 11).** Fiscal nudging received varying levels of support from respondents depending on the product: the greatest consensus was for the removal of VAT on fruit and vegetables (84.5%), 40.5% of respondents supported taxes on foods with higher added sugar, while only 23.9% supported taxes on red meat. Strongest support for these policies was seen in respondents from different countries as follows: respondents from Slovenia (52.4%) and Finland (52.3%) supported the introduction of taxes on foods with higher added sugar; respondents from Portugal (93.5%), Hungary (89.8%) and Croatia (88.7%) supported the removal of VAT on fruit and vegetables; respondents from Italy (34.1%), Bulgaria (29.1%) and Ireland (28.0%) supported the introduction of taxes on red meat production. The distribution of the 68.2% of respondents in Europe that supported all of these policies was as follows: Germany (19.1%), Italy (15.2%), France (12.6%), UK (11.6%), Spain (9.7%).

Additionally, just over a third of respondents (39.6%) supported **banning price reductions on unhealthy and unsustainable foods and drinks (Figure 11).** In this case, supporters of this policy was highest in Bulgaria (51%), France (47.6%) and Italy (47.1%). Finally, 57.9% of Europeans support the introduction of labels about environmental sustainability, most of the respondents came from Italy (68.1%), Portugal (67.8%) and Spain (66.6%).

Figure 10 Support for policies employing regulatory nudging

Figure 11 Support for other policies supporting healthier and more sustainable food systems

Box 6 – Further insights about support for new policies that promote healthy and sustainable diets.

What we learned from our in depth analyses on policy options

Topic	Insights
Policy on sustainability labels	<p><i>Supporters of a policy on sustainability labels consisted of individuals who were predominantly women, aged 50-70 years old, and held higher levels of education. These individuals tended to live in urban areas and perceived their financial situation as stable.</i></p> <p><i>From a behavioral perspective, supporters placed great importance on environmental sustainability, they were more likely to trust sustainability certifications (e.g., Fairtrade, MSC, Rainforest Alliance) and showed a strong preference for locally produced food.</i></p> <p><i>Respondents who held a slightly neutral opinion on this policy were men aged 35–54 with an intermediate level of education. They were often part-time workers, and sometimes found their income insufficient.</i></p> <p><i>Although neutral respondents recognized the value of information on the country of origin of food, they were less concerned about environmental impact than supporters of the policy. They also tended to be less engaged with sustainability certifications, placing greater emphasis on price-quality ratios when purchasing food.</i></p> <p><i>Opponents of this policy were predominantly composed of men over the age of 55 with lower education levels. They were more likely to live in rural areas and to experience financial insecurity.</i></p> <p><i>Opponents were the least concerned with sustainability issues when making food choices. They showed low trust in environmental certifications and did not prioritize factors such as carbon footprint or ethical production. They were also less likely to favor locally produced food, suggesting that other criteria—such</i></p>

as cost, taste, or availability—played a more significant role in their purchasing decisions.

Policy to increase taxes for products with high-added sugar Among **supporters**, there was a higher proportion of males. Higher levels of support were also seen among older adults aged 75 and more, those with tertiary education, and participants working full-time and retired. Additional statistical analysis showed a significant positive association with supporting the policy and the female population, those who considered their household income to meet their needs, and those who considered good quality for price while purchasing food.

Higher levels of **opposition** were observed among male participants aged 45-54 years, those unemployed and unable to work, and those of primary and lower secondary education.

Uncertainty and a neutral position was highest among females, respondents in the 18-34 age group, people unemployed and unable to work, and amongst those with lower secondary and primary education.

Policy to eliminate VAT on fruits and vegetables The policy on removing VAT on fruits and vegetables had the strongest **support** among respondents who had the following characteristics: female, older adults aged 55-74 years, those with tertiary education and participants working full-time and those who were retired.

Higher levels of **opposition** for this policy was observed for male respondents, older adults aged 75 years and more, respondents who were retired, and those who only had primary or lower secondary education.

Uncertainty (neither supported or opposed the policy and who reported, 'I don't know') was highest amongst respondents with the following characteristics: females, respondents in the 18-34 age group, those who were unemployed and unable to work, and among those with only lower secondary and primary education.

Additional statistical analyses found positive associations between this policy and perceived household income, secondary education level, and those who considered good quality for price while purchasing food.

Policy introducing tax on red meat production **Supporters** of a policy taxing red meat had the following characteristics: mainly female, 18-34 years old, with tertiary education and with full-time work.

Opposition to this policy was seen in respondents with the following characteristics: mainly male, aged 55-74 years, retired and with lower secondary education.

Respondents who were **uncertain** about this policy had the following characteristics: females, in the 18-34 age group; had an unemployed and unable to work status, and only had primary and lower secondary education.

Additional analyses revealed that respondents more likely to oppose this policy had the following characteristics: male, participants who considered their household income did not meet their needs, and those with only secondary education level.

7. Dietary patterns in Europe: Eight food consumption segments

This section presents insights on the presence “natural segments” of people who adopt homogenous behaviors in terms of consumption of different food groups. The segments have been defined by considering adherence to the planetary health diet with a specific focus on foods to encourage and foods to balance. Our analysis highlighted the presence of eight natural segments in the 27 EU countries covered in our survey⁴. The segments are presented based on the following factors: food related behaviors, facilitators and barriers to healthy and sustainable diets, and whether and to what extent they support specific policies designed to support the transition to food systems that make it easier for people in Europe to adopt healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours. The segmentation approach will be helpful in supporting the development of targeted strategies to inform both policy (at EU, national and regional levels, aligned with a multilevel governance approach) and practice.

7.1 Segment 1

Individuals in Segment 1 generally leaned towards a planetary health diet. **Their adherence was mostly driven by their consumption of whole grains, fish and shellfish, nuts, and all plant oils; however, consumption of dairy foods, animal fats, and added sugars tended to be excessive.** Nevertheless, 73.9% of them, more than the overall sample (61.2%), reported eating a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 14.6% of the overall respondent sample, and they were distributed across European countries, with a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples present in Spain (25.8%) and Croatia (20.8%), and a lower presence in Czech Republic (7.3%) and Hungary (7.8%) (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Distribution of Segment 1 across European Countries

⁴ They explain about the 85% of the variation.

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 1 had the following characteristics:

- Fewer respondents likely to be 55-74 year old
- More level 5-8 educated individuals
- More employed
- More individuals with household income valued in the fourth quartile of the national income distribution⁵
- More households with two adults and children or three adults, and more with two elderly
- More individuals who live or work in a city
- More in-healthy-weight and less obese people

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 1 had the following characteristics:

- More individuals were in charge of purchasing food
- More individuals prepared meals, even if they consumed food in restaurants or through takeaway and delivery services
- In the purchasing process, more individuals "always" or "often" considered the health and environmental elements of their food, what they typically eat or the liking of food products
- More individuals were likely to "always" consider good quality for the price of food products, packaging appearance and size

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 1 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 1 listed the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in decreasing order):

- Irregular hours of work and their busy life
- Giving up the food they like or eating food they perceive to be strange and unusual
- Difficulty to prepare
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work

This group also reported being more limited by the unaffordability of healthy and sustainable food.

The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

Policy support. People in Segment 1 reported high levels of support for policies banning marketing strategies that promote unhealthy food to children through cartoons and outdoor advertising. They would also largely support a policy that introduced 0% VAT on fruit and vegetables. Conversely, only a small proportion of them are likely to support the introduction of taxes on red meat production (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Distribution of Segment 1 across European Countries

7.2 Segment 2

In general, individuals in Segment 2 tended to lean towards a planetary health diet. Their **full adherence was to recommendations for tubers and starches, and chicken and other poultry**. However, **their consumption of vegetables, fruits, plant oils, dairy products, animal fats, and added sugars tended to be far from a planetary health diet**. For Segment 2, 57.8% of them, less than the overall sample (61.2%), reported eating a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 22.8% of the overall respondent sample, and they were generally present in many European countries, with a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples present in Czech Republic (32.6%), Slovenia (30.6%) and Slovakia (30.3%), Croatia (28.3%), Lithuania (26.4%) and Romania (26.2%), Austria (25.8%), Norway (24.9%) Hungary (24.8%) and Germany (24.6%) (Figure 14).

Figure 14 Distribution of Segment 2 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 2 had the following characteristics:

- More men
- More individuals with an intermediate level of education (ISCED 3-4)⁶Fewer individuals with household income valued in the first quartile of the national income distribution⁷
- More individuals with at least one pre-existing health condition

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 2 had the following characteristics:

- Fewer individuals were in charge of purchasing food
- Fewer individuals bought food products direct from a farmer or through online grocery delivery
- Fewer individuals prepared meals
- In the purchasing process, fewer individuals reported “always” considering health and environmental elements, the liking of food products, packaging appearance and size
- More individuals reported “often” considering the good quality for the price of food products, ease of preparing, what they typically eat.

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 2 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Overall, this group had fewer respondents with “always” and “often” answers than the total respondent sample.

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. There were not many important differences between the respondents of this segment and the total respondent sample. However, individuals in this segment more frequently reported (always or often) the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Unaffordability of healthy and sustainable food
- Giving up the food they like
- Lack of willpower

⁶ Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor’s or equivalent level, Master’s or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

⁷ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

- Difficulty to prepare their busy life
- Strong and unusual food products
- Irregular hours of work
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Lack of healthy and sustainability knowledge

Policy support. As with people in Segment 1, a large proportion of members of Segment 2 would like to support the introduction of 0% VAT on fruit and vegetables. Conversely, a smaller proportion of them were likely to support the introduction of taxes on red meat. The main difference between these first two segments was the level of support they offered for the proposed policies (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Policy support by Segment 2

7.3 Segment 3

In general, individuals in Segment 3 tended to lean towards an unhealthy, unsustainable diet regarding foods that should be encouraged (whole grains, vegetables, fruits, fish, legumes, nuts, and plant oils). However, they fully adhered to planetary health recommendations regarding tubers and starches, as well as their consumption of dairy, chicken, and eggs. Their self-assessment was coherent with their profile, indeed only the 42.5% of them reported to eat a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 14.7% of the overall respondent sample, and they made up a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples in the following European countries: Czech Republic (20.6%), Austria (19.7%), Germany (18.6%) and Belgium (18.1%). They had a lower presence in Spain (6.6%) and Portugal (6.7%) (Figure 16).

Figure 16 Distribution of Segment 3 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 3 had the following characteristics:

- More 45-75 year old individuals
- More men
- More individuals with a medium or low educational level (ISCED0-2 and ISCED3-4)⁸
- More unemployed
- More individuals with household income valued in the first quartile of the national income distribution Q1⁹
- More individuals in a household with one person
- Fewer individuals in a household with two adults and children, and less than two elderly
- Fewer individuals who lived or worked in a city
- More individuals who were overweight or obese

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 3 had the following characteristics:

- Fewer individuals were in charge of purchasing food
- More individuals bought food products in only one supermarket
- Fewer individuals prepared meals which were mostly ready-made from shops/supermarkets
- In the purchasing/consumption process, fewer individuals “always” or “often” considered health, environmental and ethical factor, good quality for the price of food products, the availability of food products where individuals usually shop, the foods which they typically eat, and the liking of food products, as well as the package appearance and size.
- More individuals never considered religious aspects when they purchased or consumed food products

⁸ Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor’s or equivalent level, Master’s or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

⁹ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 3 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food product where they usually shop
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Though the facilitators of Segment 3 are in the same order as for Segment 2, it is important to note that these factors are “always” or “often” recognized as facilitator much less frequently as compared to the overall respondent sample.

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. There were not many important differences between the respondents of this segment and the total respondent sample. However, individuals in this segment more frequently reported (always or often) the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Unaffordability of healthy and sustainable food, though less than Segments 1 and 2
- Lack of willpower
- Giving up the food they like
- Difficulty to prepare
- Strange and unusual food products
- Their busy life and lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diet
- Irregular hours of work
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work, though this was less than Segment 1.

Policy support. In this segment, fewer respondents supported policies that banned the sale of unhealthy food and drinks to young people, and marketing strategies for unhealthy food at supermarket checkouts. As with Segments 1 and 2, there was strong support for a policy of no VAT on fruits and vegetables (Figure 17).

Figure 17

Policy support by Segment 3

7.4 Segment 4

Individuals in Segment 4 tended to lean towards a planetary health diet. They fully adhered to the recommendations for consumption of all plant oils, tubers, chicken, and eggs. However, the consumption of dairy products tended to be excessive. Overall, it appeared to be one of the best performers in terms of adherence to healthy and sustainable diets. Their self-assessment is coherent with their profile, with 80.7% of them reporting adherence to a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

The members of this segment constituted 14.2% of the overall respondent sample with a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples present in Italy (28.9%), Greece (28.6%) and Spain (18.5%) and a lower presence in Latvia (5.8%) and Estonia (5.0%) (Figure 18).

Figure 18 Distribution of Segment 4 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 4 had the following characteristics:

- More individuals who were 55 years old and more
- More women
- More individuals with a high educational level (ISCED5-8)¹⁰
- More retired individuals
- Slightly fewer individuals with household income valued in the first quartile of the national income distribution¹¹
- More individuals in a household with three or more adults
- Fewer individuals in a household with two adults and children
- Fewer individuals in a household with no elderly
- More individuals who had a healthy weight and fewer individuals who were overweight or obese

¹⁰ Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor's or equivalent level, Master's or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

¹¹ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 4 had the following characteristics:

- More individuals were in charge of purchasing food
- More individuals bought food products in only two or more supermarkets or in local markets
- More individuals prepared meals at home
- In the purchasing/consumption process, more individuals “always” or “often” considered health, environmental and ethical elements, good quality for the price of food products, and the liking of food products
- Fewer individuals considered religious aspects

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 4 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals for health, knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets, and the availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop (Segment 4 considered these factors more than Segment 1)
- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them and practical tools (though this was less than in Segment 1)
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Generally, this segment recognized the proposed factors as barriers less than individuals in Segments 1-3. However, individuals in this segment more frequently reported (always or often) as being factors that limited their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Unaffordability of healthy and sustainable food (similar to Segment 3)
- Giving up the food they like
- Their busy life and lack of willpower
- Difficulty to prepare healthy and sustainable food
- Irregular hours of work, eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with, and unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diet

Policy support. More than any other segment, Segment 4 was likely to support all the policies proposed to promote a healthier and more sustainable food system (Figure 19).

Figure 19

Policy support by Segment 4

7.5 Segment 5

In general, this segment tended to lean towards an unhealthy, unsustainable diet regarding foods that should be encouraged (whole grains, vegetables, fruits, fish, legumes, nuts, and plant oils) and some foods to balance like dairy products and animal fats. However, they fully adhered to planetary health diet recommendations regarding tubers and starches, as well as their consumption of chicken and eggs. Their self-assessment was in line with their consumption habits, indeed only the 36.2% of them reported eating a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 9% of the overall respondent sample. This segment was present in a larger proportion of country-specific respondent pools in Czech Republic (17.7%), while very few were present in Italy (2.6%), Spain (2.3%) and Greece (2.1%) (Figure 20).

Figure 20 Distribution of Segment 5 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the overall total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 5 had the following characteristics:

- Fewer individuals younger than 45 years and more individuals in the 55-74 years band
- Fewer individual with a high educational level (ISCED 5-8)¹²
- More retired or unemployed individuals
- More individuals with household income valued in the first quartile of the national income distribution and fewer in the fourth quartile¹³
- More households with one adult or with two adults
- Fewer individuals who lived or worked in a city
- More individuals who lived in a small city or in a country village
- Fewer who were of a healthy-weight and more people who were obese (25%)

¹² Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor's or equivalent level, Master's or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

¹³ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 5 had the following characteristics:

- More individuals were in charge of purchasing food
- Fewer individuals purchased food products in independent stores, butchers, grocers, local markets, direct from a farmer and online grocery delivery
- Fewer individuals frequently prepared meals, but they were more likely to consume home made meals, similar to segment 4
- In the purchasing process, fewer individuals "always" or "often" considered health and environmental factors
- Slightly more respondents "always" considered availability of food where they usually buy food, while fewer considered good quality for food product prices
- More individuals "always" considered, in descending order: good quality for the price of food products, packaging appearance and size
- Individuals did not consider religious aspects very frequently

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 5 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with and expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Generally, the percentage of individuals reported a lower percentage in scores 4 ("often") and 5 ("always") for all the above factors than Segments 1-4.

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Generally, the proposed factors limited individuals in this segment less frequently compared with the overall total respondent sample, except for the lack of willpower which is higher for Segment 5 compared to the general population.

Respondents in Segment 5 reported the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in decreasing order):

- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Lack of willpower
- Giving up the food they like
- Difficulty to prepare healthy and sustainable foods
- Eating food they perceive to be strange and unusual
- Their busy life
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Irregular hours of work
- Lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diets

Policy support. This segment was less likely to support policies that promote the use of labels indicating environmental sustainability, the introduction of taxes on products with high added sugar content or on red meat, the banning of the placement of unhealthy food at supermarket checkouts, or

the banning of discounts on unhealthy food and drinks. They did, however, support policies of no VAT on fruits and vegetables and banning the sale of unhealthy drinks to young people (Figure 21).

Figure 21 Policy support by Segment 5

7.6 Segment 6

In general, the members of Segment 6 tended to lean towards a healthy and sustainable diet consisting of **vegetables, fruits, and legumes**. However, they did not adhere to planetary health diet recommendations regarding **all plant oils and dairy products**, and they consumed very large **amounts of animal fats and added sugars**. Their self-assessment was, in part, aligned with their consumption pattern with 53.7% of them reporting to eat a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 8.2% of the overall respondent sample with a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples present in Estonia (16.8%), Ireland (16.2%), Latvia (16.2%), Lithuania (15.7%) and Poland (15.0%); there was a lower proportion of Segment 6 in Greece (3.8%) and Italy (2.2%) (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Distribution of Segment 6 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 1 had the following characteristics:

- More individuals aged 18-34 years
- Fewer individuals in the 55 and older age bands
- Fewer individuals with low education (ISCED0-2) and more individuals with a high educational level (ISCED 5-8)¹⁴
- More employed individuals (62.5%) similarly to Segment 1 and fewer retired individuals
- More households with two adults and children, and without elderly
- Fewer households with only one person
- Fewer individuals who lived in a city
- More individuals who worked in a small city or in a country village
- No significant differences in terms of BMI

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 6 had the following characteristics:

- Slightly fewer individuals were “always” in charge of purchasing food and bought food in one or more supermarkets
- Slightly more individuals “always” prepared meals, but they consumed slightly more takeaway food
- In the purchasing process, fewer individuals “always” or “often” considered health and environmental elements such as (in decreasing order): ingredient list, information on country of food origin, seasonality, food nutritional values, and environmental impact
- More individuals “always” considered good quality for the price of food products, packaging appearance and size

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Overall, there were no marked differences between this group and the overall respondent sample. Respondents in Segment 6 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Segment 6 generally had tendencies similar to those observed for Segment 1 and Segment 4.

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Generally, most of the proposed factors were more frequently chosen by members of this segment compared with the overall respondent sample,

¹⁴ Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor’s or equivalent level, Master’s or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

especially their busy life, irregular working hours and lack of willpower. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 6 reported the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in decreasing order):

- Unaffordability of healthy and sustainable diets
- Giving up the food they like
- Lack of willpower
- Their busy life
- Irregular hours of work
- Difficulty to prepare healthy and sustainable food
- Eating food they perceive to be strange and unusual
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with
- Lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diet

Policy support. As for Segment 4, Segment 6 strongly supports zero VAT on fruit and vegetables, as well as banning the sale of unhealthy drinks to young people. This segment was, however, less likely to support tax on red meat (Figure 23).

Figure 23 Policy support by Segment 6

7.7 Segment 7

Overall, Segment 7 tended to lean towards a healthy and sustainable diet. They mostly adhere to planetary health diet recommendations regarding **tubers, starches, red meat, chicken, and eggs**. However, their consumption of **whole grains, vegetables, fruits, and plant oils** tended to be low. Interestingly, their self-assessment was not coherent with their profile with 70.5% of respondents reporting to eat a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

Members of this segment constituted 10.6% of the overall population and a larger proportion of country-specific respondent samples were present in Greece (18.4%) and Italy (21.5%). In most other countries, the presence of segment members was just under 10% (Figure 24).

Figure 24 Distribution of Segment 7 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. The profile of this segment was similar to that of the total respondent sample, except for:

- Sex – they were mostly female
- Job status, there were more retired and fewer employed individuals
- Income: there were more individuals in the first quartile of the national income distribution¹⁵,
- More households with two persons
- Fewer households with two persons and children and without elderly
- BMI: there were more people with a healthy weight and fewer obese individuals

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 7 had the following characteristics:

- Individuals bought food in one supermarket more frequently
- Fewer purchased food in other available options
- Individuals consumed fewer ready-made meals from shop/supermarket, takeaway and restaurants
- In the purchasing process, more individuals “always” or “often” considered health and environmental elements such as (in decreasing order): ingredient list, seasonality, information on country of food origin, food nutritional values, local production, environmental friendly packaging, ethical and sustainable production, and environmental impact
- Fewer individuals considered religious aspects

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Overall, there were no marked differences between this segment and the total respondent sample except for the knowledge that individuals have about healthy and sustainable diets. Respondents in Segment 7 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production

¹⁵ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Generally, Segment 7 had tendencies similar to those observed for Segment 6.

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Generally, most of the proposed factors were less limiting for respondents in Segment 7 except for lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diets and irregular working hours. **Respondents in Segment 7 reported the following factors as limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in decreasing order):**

- Unaffordability of healthy and sustainable diets
- Giving up the food they like
- Their busy life
- Irregular hours of work and lack of willpower
- Difficulty to prepare healthy and sustainable food
- Lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diet
- Eating foods they perceive to be strange and unusual food
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Eating habits or behaviors of people they share meals with

Overall, this segment reported medium frequencies of “always” and “often” responses for the above barriers compared with Segments 1-6.

Policy support. As with Segments 1 and 6, individuals in Segment 7 were more likely to support the introduction of an environmental sustainability label and were also supportive of no VAT on fruits and vegetables (Figure 25).

Figure 25

Policy support by Segment 7

7.8 Segment 8

Individuals in Segment 8 leaned heavily towards a healthy and sustainable diet, based on consumption patterns of foods such as **whole grains, fish, legumes, nuts, and plant oils**. However, they consumed **large amounts of foods that the planetary health diet suggests balancing**. Their self-assessment was

not coherent with their food consumption pattern with 74.5% of them reporting eating a healthy and sustainable diet most of the time.

This segment constituted 5.9% of the overall respondent sample with a larger proportion of the country-specific respondent samples present in Portugal (14.6%), Ireland (13.8%), Latvia (11.1%) and Estonia (10.2%). In most other countries, the presence of this segment was under 5% (Figure 26).

Figure 26 Distribution of Segment 8 across European Countries

In summary:

Profile. In comparison with total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 8 had the following characteristics::

- More individuals aged 18-44 years
- Fewer individuals in the 55 and older age bands
- More women
- More individuals with higher education (ISCED 5-8)¹⁶
- More employed individuals (62.5%)
- Fewer retired and unemployed individuals
- More individuals in the fourth quartile of the national income distribution¹⁷
- Fewer individuals in the first and second quartile of the national income distribution
- More households with children notwithstanding the number of adults, and more without elderly (more than in other segments)
- Fewer households without children
- More individuals who lived in a city and worked in a city or in the suburbs
- More individuals without pre-existing health conditions
- More individuals who were underweight or had a healthy weight, and fewer individuals who were overweight or obese

¹⁶ Educational attainment level according to ISCED 2011:

ISCED_0-2: Early childhood education, Primary education, Lower secondary education.

ISCED_3-4: Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education.

ISCED_5-8: Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor's or equivalent level, Master's or equivalent level, Doctoral or equivalent level.

¹⁷ The first quartile (Q1) of the national income distribution includes the lowest incomes, while the fourth quartile (Q4) includes the highest.

Food purchasing and consumption behaviors. Compared with the total respondent sample, respondents in Segment 8 had the following characteristics:

- The highest percentage of individuals who purchased and prepared food products and meals
- They were used to buying in all the categories of food product suppliers, and their meals came from home less frequently
- In the purchasing process, more individuals “always” considered health and environmental factors, largely higher than the total respondent sample
- More individuals “always” considered the ingredient list and nutritional values among the health and environmental related factors
- More individuals “always” considered good quality for the price of food products, packaging appearance and size, the liking products and food that they typically eat
- More individuals “always” and “often” considered religious aspects (19.5% and 22.5%, respectively)

Factors facilitating adherence to the planetary health diet. Overall, there were marked differences between this segment and the total respondent sample, especially compared to Segment 1 when specific drivers are considered. Respondents in Segment 8 more frequently (always or often) found the following factors supporting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in descending order):

- Their personal goals regarding health
- Their knowledge about healthy and sustainable diets
- The availability of healthy and sustainable food products where they usually shop
- Expectations to be healthy by people who are important to them
- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with
- Information about the sustainability and ethics of production
- Practical tools
- External pressure (media, etc.)

Factors limiting adherence to the planetary health diet. Generally, more than half of respondents in Segment 8 reported the unaffordability of healthy and sustainable diets and the risk to give up the food they like as factors limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet. **Respondents in Segment 7 reported the following factors as** limiting their adherence to the planetary health diet (in decreasing order):

- Eating habits or behaviours of people they share meals with
- Unavailability of healthy and sustainable food close to where they live or work
- Irregular hours of work
- Lack of knowledge on healthy and sustainable diet
- Their busy life
- Eating food they perceive to be strange and unusual
- Difficulty to prepare healthy and sustainable food
- Lack of willpower

Overall, this segment reported higher frequencies of “always” and “often” responses for the above limiting factors compared with Segments 1-7.

Policy support. This segment reported the lowest percentage of supporters of 0% VAT on fruit and vegetables (Figure 27). There were no other very marked differences in policy views as compared to Segments 1-7.

Figure 27 Policy support by Segment 8

Conclusions

As far as the authors are aware, this is the largest and most comprehensive cross-sectional survey conducted to date on adherence to, and barriers and facilitators affected adherence to, the EAT-Lancet planetary health diet in Europe.

Current research on mapping and monitoring dietary behaviours in Europe has several limitations including only conducting the survey in a small number of countries, in some instances targeting specific subgroups of the population and using different survey methods and tools. The approach taken in FEAST aimed to overcome these barriers while also advancing the state of the art. There are areas where our contributions can support both academic and non-academic partners as well as those working on practice and policy to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour in Europe.

- Our simplified and streamlined food frequency questionnaire is much less cumbersome to complete as compared to typical food frequency questionnaires while still being able to collect the most important data on adherence to healthy and sustainable diets, in this case utilising the recommendations of the EAT-Lancet planetary health diet.
- An aggregate index of the most important barriers and facilitators impacting individuals' dietary behaviours
- An aggregate index of important policies that could support the transitions to healthier and more sustainable food systems
- The combination of our sampling approach and use of a survey provider with a very large panel, provided by CINT, allowed us to have a sample across multiple countries that trended towards being nationally representative. We acknowledge that there will still be some bias in the sample because this was a digital survey and we still relied on a panel, but given the size and scope and representation across multiple population subgroups across Europe, it is still quite a powerful sample.
- Our utilisation of novel statistical methods to calculate adherence to the planetary health diet through the ELFI index
- Our segmentation approach which can be used across different barriers and facilitators to adherence to the planetary health diet alongside subgroup characteristics allowed us to identify eight Natural European Dietary Segments that can serve to provide powerful insights on policies and practice that are more/less likely to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours in Europe.

The analyses of our survey results also revealed several important findings:

- There was a general lack of adherence to the planetary health diet across Europe, despite respondents thinking they are adhering to a healthy and sustainable diet. This reveals a knowledge gap that can be a source of intervention.
- There was marked variation in adherence to the planetary health diet between European countries, which can serve as a marker and/or driver of health inequalities
- Given the heterogeneous distribution of the eight natural segments within and between countries, this also reveals a further source of variation that can impact health inequalities
- The differences between the eight natural dietary segments provides insights into approaches that can be taken to customise interventions to meet the preferences and needs of different population subgroups to support their transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours
- From a policy perspective, the majority of respondents showed strong support for 0% VAT on fruits and vegetables and policies aimed at keeping children healthy such as through banning energy drink marketing directed towards children

Finally, the methods and tools developed in WP2 can be used by a variety of stakeholders to inform policy and track its impact (taking a multilevel governance perspective, the survey could be used by the EU, national and regional governments) as well as informing and supporting the evaluation of different interventions aimed at supporting the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours across Europe.

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